

**APPROACHING CUSICK'S CONJECTURE ON THE
SUM-OF-DIGITS FUNCTION**

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Abstract

Cusick's conjecture on the binary sum of digits $s(n)$ of a nonnegative integer n states the following: for all nonnegative integers t we have

$$c_t = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} |\{n < N : s(n+t) \geq s(n)\}| > 1/2.$$

We prove that for given $\varepsilon > 0$ we have $c_t + c_{t'} > 1 - \varepsilon$ if the binary expansion of t contains enough blocks of consecutive 1s (depending on ε), where $t' = 3 \cdot 2^\lambda - t$ and λ is chosen such that $2^\lambda \leq t < 2^{\lambda+1}$.

1. Introduction

The binary sum-of-digits function s is defined by

$$s(\varepsilon_\nu 2^\nu + \cdots + \varepsilon_0 2^0) = \varepsilon_\nu + \cdots + \varepsilon_0$$

for all digits $\varepsilon_i \in \{0, 1\}$. It is an elementary yet difficult problem to consider the behavior of s under addition of a constant. T. W. Cusick (private communication, 2011) proposed the following conjecture.

Conjecture 1. For a nonnegative integer t , define

$$c_t = \text{dens}\{n \geq 0 : s(n+t) \geq s(n)\},$$

where $\text{dens } A$ denotes the asymptotic density of a set $A \subseteq \mathbb{N}$. Then $c_t > 1/2$.

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We note that the set in question is in fact a finite union of arithmetic progressions, so there are no problems of convergence (see Bésineau [1]). This conjecture arose when Cusick was working on a related conjecture due to Tu and Deng [13, 14], which concerns binary addition modulo $2^k - 1$. Tu and Deng’s conjecture is of interest since it allows constructing Boolean functions with desirable cryptographic properties. Partial results on the Tu–Deng conjecture have been obtained; see, for example, [2, 4, 9, 11]. Moreover, both Cusick’s conjecture and the Tu–Deng conjecture have been proven *asymptotically*, the former by Drmota, Kauers, and the author [5], and the latter by Wallner and the author [12], but the full statements are still open. In particular, we wish to note that no bound of the form $c_t > a$ or $c_t < b$ for some $a > 0$ or $b < 1$, valid for all $t \geq 0$, is known! In this paper we concentrate on Cusick’s conjecture. The abovementioned result by Drmota, Kauers and the author [5] is the following: we have $c_t > 1/2$ for almost all t in the sense of asymptotic density, that is,

$$\text{dens}\{t : c_t > 1/2\} = 1.$$

However, this theorem does not tell us anything about the structure of such a set of “good” t ; it does not provide a statement allowing to extract many examples of integers t satisfying Cusick’s conjecture.

The present paper constitutes a step in this direction. More precisely, since the original conjecture is elusive and too hard, we consider a simplified version. In order to formulate this easier statement and our main theorem, we define $t' = 3 \cdot 2^\lambda - t$, where $2^\lambda \leq t < 2^{\lambda+1}$.

Conjecture 2 (Cusick, simplified). For all $t \geq 0$, we have $c_t + c_{t'} > 1$. In other words, at least one out of t or t' satisfies Cusick’s conjecture.

Our main theorem is an approximation to this simplified conjecture.

Theorem 1. *Assume that $\varepsilon > 0$. There exists a constant $C = C(\varepsilon)$ such that*

$$c_t + c_{t'} > 1 - \varepsilon,$$

if the binary expansion of t contains at least C blocks of consecutive 1s.

We note that an admissible value of $C(\varepsilon)$ can be made completely explicit. Note also that this theorem gives a lower bound $c_t > 1/2 - \varepsilon$ for many values of t : in fact, the number of integers $0 \leq t < T$ having less than C blocks of consecutive 1s in its binary expansion is bounded by T^η for some $\eta < 1$. The important point is the fact that obtain a very efficient method of finding many t such that $c_t > 1/2 - \varepsilon$: we only have to start with an integer having sufficiently many blocks of 1s and possibly invert the digits between the first and the last 1 (corresponding to $t \mapsto t'$) in order to arrive at such a t .

The remainder of this paper is dedicated to the proof of Theorem 1. Throughout the proof, we use the common notations $e(x) = \exp(2\pi ix)$ and $\|x\| = \min_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} |x - k|$.

2. Proof of the Main Theorem

For $t \geq 0$ and $k \in \mathbb{Z}$, we define the densities

$$\delta(k, t) = \text{dens}\{n \in \mathbb{N} : s(n + t) - s(n) = k\}.$$

Again, these densities exist [1]. These values satisfy the recurrence [5]

$$\begin{aligned} \delta(k, 1) &= \begin{cases} 2^{k-2}, & k \leq 1; \\ 0 & \text{otherwise;} \end{cases} \\ \delta(k, 2t) &= \delta(k, t); \\ \delta(k, 2t + 1) &= \frac{1}{2}\delta(k - 1, t) + \frac{1}{2}\delta(k + 1, t + 1). \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, we define a simplified array φ by modifying the start vector:

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(k, 1) &= \begin{cases} 1, & k = 0; \\ 0 & \text{otherwise;} \end{cases} \\ \varphi(k, 2t) &= \varphi(k, t); \\ \varphi(k, 2t + 1) &= \frac{1}{2}\varphi(k - 1, t) + \frac{1}{2}\varphi(k + 1, t + 1). \end{aligned}$$

The reason for the introduction of this array, and in fact also the reason for the definition of t' , is the following symmetry property [5]: we have

$$\varphi(k, t) = \varphi(-k, t').$$

Moreover, by linearity we have

$$\delta(k, t) = \sum_{\ell+s=k} \varphi(\ell, t)\delta(s, 1) = \sum_{\ell \geq 0} \varphi(k + 1 - \ell)2^{-\ell-1}.$$

We obtain

$$\begin{aligned} c_t + c_{t'} &= \sum_{\ell \geq -1} (\varphi(\ell, t) + \varphi(-\ell, t)) (1 - 2^{-\ell-2}) \\ &= \frac{3}{2}\varphi(0, t) + \frac{11}{8}\varphi(1, t) + \frac{11}{8}\varphi(-1, t) \\ &\quad + \sum_{\ell \geq 2} (1 - 2^{-\ell-2}) (\varphi(\ell, t) + \varphi(-\ell, t)). \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Remark 1. From the above identity we immediately obtain $c_t + c_{t'} \geq 15/16$ by using the identity $\sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} \varphi(k, t) = 1$; it is obvious to suspect that the maximum of $\varphi(k, t)$ is attained for $|k| \leq 1$. This would yield $c_t > 1/2$ or $c_{t'} > 1/2$ and thus settle the simplified form of Cusick’s conjecture. However, this assumption is wrong: for

$t = 149$ the maximum is attained at the position $k = 2$. Still, there is hope: in fact, it is sufficient to prove that

$$\varphi(-1, t) + \varphi(0, t) + \varphi(1, t) \geq \varphi(k, t) \quad \text{for all } k \text{ such that } |k| \geq 2. \tag{2}$$

This can be seen as follows: under this hypothesis we have

$$\begin{aligned} c_t + c_{t'} &\geq \sum_{|\ell| \geq 2} \varphi(\ell, t) - \sum_{|\ell| \geq 2} 2^{-|\ell|-2} \max_{|\ell| \geq 2} \varphi(\ell, t) \\ &\quad + \varphi(-1, t) + \varphi(0, t) + \varphi(1, t) + \frac{3}{8} (\varphi(-1, t) + \varphi(0, t) + \varphi(1, t)) \\ &\geq 1 + \max_{|\ell| \geq 2} \varphi(\ell, t) \left(\frac{3}{8} - \sum_{|\ell| \geq 2} 2^{-|\ell|-2} \right) > 1. \end{aligned}$$

It looks like a simple thing to prove (2) by induction on the length of the binary expansion of t , using the recurrence for φ ; however, so far we did not succeed.

We are going to work with the following expression, where $\vartheta \in \mathbb{R}$.

$$\omega_t(\vartheta) = \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} \varphi(k, t) e(k\vartheta). \tag{3}$$

Obviously, this sum is absolutely convergent.

Our strategy is to give an upper bound for $|\omega_t(\vartheta)|$, where $\vartheta = j/m$. This will give us some information on the behavior of $k \mapsto \varphi(k, t)$ on residue classes $b + m\mathbb{Z}$. For each b , we take the least weight appearing in (1) for $\ell \in b + m\mathbb{Z}$ and multiply it with the sum $\sum_{\ell \in b + m\mathbb{Z}} \varphi(\ell, t)$; afterwards, we sum the contributions of the different residue classes, using the argument on the smallness of $\omega_t(j/m)$.

Lemma 1. *We have the following recurrence for the values $\omega_t(\vartheta)$:*

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_1(\vartheta) &= 1, \\ \omega_{2t}(\vartheta) &= \omega_t(\vartheta), \\ \omega_{2t+1} &= \frac{e(\vartheta)}{2} \omega_t(\vartheta) + \frac{e(-\vartheta)}{2} \omega_{t+1}(\vartheta). \end{aligned}$$

The proof is straightforward, using the recurrence for φ . This new recurrence can be written using 2×2 -matrices [10]: define

$$A_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ e(\vartheta)/2 & e(-\vartheta)/2 \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad A_1 = \begin{pmatrix} e(\vartheta)/2 & e(-\vartheta)/2 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

If $t = (\varepsilon_\nu \cdots \varepsilon_0)_2$ is the binary representation of $t \geq 1$, we have

$$\omega_t(\vartheta) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} A_{\varepsilon_0} \cdots A_{\varepsilon_{\nu-1}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Lemma 2. *Assume that the binary expansion of $t \geq 1$ contains at least $2M + 1$ blocks of consecutive 1s. Then*

$$|\omega_t(\vartheta)| \leq \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}\|\vartheta\|^2\right)^M.$$

Proof. There are at least M positions $j \in \{0, \dots, \nu - 3\}$, having distance ≥ 3 from each other, such that $(\varepsilon_j, \varepsilon_{j+1}, \varepsilon_{j+2}) = (100)$ or $(\varepsilon_j, \varepsilon_{j+1}, \varepsilon_{j+2}) = (101)$. We show that for such a block we gain a factor of $1 - \|\vartheta\|^2/2$. Using the row-sum norm $\|\cdot\|_\infty$ for matrices, which is derived from the maximum norm for vectors and which is sub-multiplicative, it is sufficient to prove that

$$\|A_1A_0A_0\|_\infty \leq 1 - \frac{1}{2}\|\vartheta\|^2 \quad \text{and} \quad \|A_1A_0A_1\|_\infty \leq 1 - \frac{1}{2}\|\vartheta\|^2.$$

After a short calculation we obtain

$$A_1A_0A_0 = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{e(\vartheta)}{2} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{e(-\vartheta)}{8} & \frac{e(-3\vartheta)}{8} \\ \frac{e(\vartheta)}{2} + \frac{1}{4} & \frac{e(-2\vartheta)}{4} \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{and}$$

$$A_1A_0A_1 = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{e(2\vartheta)}{4} + \frac{e(\vartheta)}{8} & \frac{1}{4} + \frac{e(-2\vartheta)}{4} + \frac{e(-\vartheta)}{8} \\ \frac{e(2\vartheta)}{4} & \frac{e(-\vartheta)}{2} + \frac{1}{4} \end{pmatrix},$$

and we see that the row-sum norm is strictly below 1 as soon as $\vartheta \notin \mathbb{Z}$. More precisely, we use [3, Lemme 3], stating that

$$\left| \frac{1}{q}(1 + z_1 + \dots + z_{q-1}) \right| \leq 1 - \frac{1}{2q} \max_{1 \leq j < q} (1 - \Re z_j)$$

for $|z_1|, \dots, |z_{q-1}| \leq 1$. For example, the left upper entry of $A_1A_0A_0$ can be bounded as follows:

$$\left| \frac{e(\vartheta)}{2} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{e(-\vartheta)}{8} \right| = \frac{7}{8} \left| \frac{1}{7}(1 + 1 + e(-\vartheta) + 4 \cdot e(\vartheta)) \right| \leq \frac{7}{8} \left(1 - \frac{1}{14}(1 - \Re e(\vartheta)) \right).$$

Analogously, the entry below, and also the right lower entry of $A_1A_0A_1$, may be bounded by

$$\frac{3}{4} \left| \frac{1}{3}(1 + 2 \cdot e(\vartheta)) \right| \leq \frac{3}{4} \left(1 - \frac{1}{6}(1 - \Re e(\vartheta)) \right),$$

while the right upper entry of this second matrix can be bounded by

$$\frac{5}{8} \left(1 - \frac{1}{10}(1 - \Re e(\vartheta)) \right).$$

It follows that $\|B\|_\infty \leq 1 - \frac{1}{16}(1 - \Re e(\vartheta))$ for $B \in \{A_1A_0A_0, A_1A_0A_1\}$. Moreover, we have the elementary inequality $\Re e(\vartheta) = \cos(2\pi\vartheta) \leq 1 - 8\|\vartheta\|^2$, so that $\|B\| \leq 1 - \frac{1}{2}\|\vartheta\|^2$. This proves the lemma. \square

We are interested in the quantity

$$\psi(b, m, t) = \sum_{\ell \in b+m\mathbb{Z}} \varphi(\ell, t).$$

Moreover, we define

$$\tilde{a}_\ell = \begin{cases} 3/2, & \text{if } \ell = 0; \\ 11/8, & \text{if } |\ell| = 1; \\ 1 - 2^{-|\ell|-2}, & \text{if } |\ell| \geq 2. \end{cases}$$

Clearly $\tilde{a}_\ell \geq a_\ell := 1 - 2^{-|\ell|-2}$ for all $\ell \in \mathbb{Z}$. By (1), we obtain

$$c_t + c_{t'} \geq \sum_{0 \leq b < m} \psi(b, m, t) \min_{\ell \in b+m\mathbb{Z}} a_\ell. \tag{4}$$

By monotonicity and symmetry of a_ℓ , we obtain

$$\min_{\ell \in b+m\mathbb{Z}} a_\ell = \begin{cases} 1 - 2^{-b-2} & \text{if } 0 \leq b < m/2 \\ 1 - 2^{-(m-b)-2} & \text{if } m/2 \leq b < m. \end{cases} \tag{5}$$

Moreover,

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(b, m, t) &= \sum_{\ell \in b+m\mathbb{Z}} \varphi(\ell, t) = \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} \varphi(k, t) \frac{1}{m} \sum_{0 \leq j < m} e\left(j \frac{k-b}{m}\right) \\ &= \frac{1}{m} \sum_{0 \leq j < m} e\left(-\frac{jb}{m}\right) \omega_t(j/m). \end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 2 it follows (using the abbreviation $x \pm y$ to stand for $x + O(y)$ with an implied constant 1) that

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(b, m, t) &= \frac{1}{m} \pm \max_{1 \leq j < m} |\omega_t(j/m)| \\ &= \frac{1}{m} \pm (1 - 1/(2m^2))^M = \frac{1}{m} \pm e^{-M/(2m^2)}, \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

if t has at least $2M + 1$ blocks of consecutive 1s in its binary expansion.

From (4) and (6) it follows that

$$c_t + c_{t'} \geq \frac{1}{m} \sum_{0 \leq b < m} \min_{\ell \in b+m\mathbb{Z}} a_\ell \pm me^{-M/(2m^2)}.$$

It remains to consider mean values of the quantity in (5). It is obvious that this mean value converges to 1 for $m \rightarrow \infty$; quantitatively, we get for all $N \leq m$

$$\sum_{0 \leq b < m} \min_{\ell \in b+m\mathbb{Z}} a_\ell \geq \sum_{N \leq b < m-N} \min_{\ell \in b+m\mathbb{Z}} a_\ell \geq (m - 2N) (1 - 2^{-N-2})$$

$$\geq m(1 - 2^{-N-2}) - 2N.$$

We obtain

$$c_t + c_{t'} \geq 1 - 2^{-N-2} - \frac{2N}{m} - me^{-M/(2m^2)}.$$

Let $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ be given. We aim to define a bound C as in the statement of the theorem. Let $N = \lfloor -\log_2 \varepsilon \rfloor + 1$. Then clearly $2^{-N-2} < \varepsilon/3$. Moreover, choose $m = \lfloor 6N/\varepsilon \rfloor + 1$, then $2N/m < \varepsilon/3$. Finally, let $M = \lfloor -2m^2 \log(\varepsilon/(3m)) \rfloor + 1$, so that $me^{-M/(2m^2)} < \varepsilon/3$. The choice $C = 2M + 1$ satisfies the claim of the theorem. Asymptotically, an admissible choice for C is given by $\alpha(\log \varepsilon)^3/\varepsilon^2$ for some constant $\alpha < 0$ that can be given explicitly.

Remark 2. It would be desirable to improve our theorem in one or more of the following three aspects:

1. Prove statements on individual c_t instead of the combined quantity $c_t + c_{t'}$.
2. Eliminate the quantity ε appearing in our lower bound.
3. Prove statements for *all* $t \geq 0$ instead of demanding the existence of many blocks of 1s in the binary expansion of t .

Of course, Cusick's original conjecture corresponds to (1) \wedge (2) \wedge (3), while the simplified form given above corresponds to (2) \wedge (3).

We expect that progress on (1) can be made by appealing to the study of moments of the probability distribution defined by $k \mapsto \delta(k, t)$ initiated by Emme and Prikhod'ko [8] and pursued by Emme and Hubert [7, 6]. This will be the subject of a future research paper.

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